

LA EXPERIENCIA DEL REUSO

ACTAS CONGRESO INTERNACIONAL
Propuestas para la Documentación, Restauración
y Reutilización del Patrimonio Arquitectónico

VOLUMEN I

●
CRITERIO Y MÉTODO EN ÉPOCA DE CRISIS

INGENIERÍA Y TÉCNICA AL SERVICIO DE LA RESTAURACIÓN

**Actas del Congreso Internacional sobre
Documentación, Restauración y
Reutilización del Patrimonio Arquitectónico**

VOL. I

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La Organización del Congreso sobre Documentación, Conservación y Reutilización del Patrimonio Arquitectónico celebrado en Madrid en Junio de 2013, con la colaboración del Dipartimento di Architettura de la Università degli Studi di Firenze, tuvo especial interés en que las Actas del Congreso estuvieran impresas en papel, con anterioridad al mismo para poderlas dar a los asistentes al comienzo del mismo.

Todo el trabajo previo tuvo que hacerse con mucha rapidez, con un calendario muy estricto y los esfuerzos debidos a la gran cantidad de trabajos presentados y a la escasez de medios, por lo que se pide excusas por los posibles errores que pudiera haber habido y que con esta edición digital se intentan subsanar.

Contamos también con una nueva aportación, excepcional, que agradecemos extraordinariamente, la del Profesor Lorenzo Jurita, ingeniero, del Dipartimento di Architettura, Ingegneria delle Costruzioni e Ambiente Costruito (ABC) del Politecnico de Milano.

Con ello se enriquece extraordinariamente el ámbito de la ingeniería al servicio del Patrimonio, donde el conocimiento y el respeto a los valores documentales del Patrimonio Arquitectónico, quedan protegidos y valorados con sus excepcionales aportaciones a la consolidación de la consistencia física de este patrimonio construido.

Muchas gracias.

SM

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Semiautomatic techniques for the representation of painted vaults in true size of palazzo Pitti in Florence

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The Grand Duchess Vittoria della Rovere and Serenissimi Sposi's Apartments on the ground floor of the Pitti Palace were decorated by Jacopo Chiavistelli and his team after the second half of 1600. The illusionistic characteristic perspective paintings cover the walls and vaults with representations of architecture and figures in order to expand the physical space of the rooms.

The vaults are the conclusion and the most majestic expression of the entire perspective scheme and order to secure their preservation, diagnostics and restoration, a true size representation of decorations is required.

Thanks to the introduction of digital three-dimensional survey with laser scanners, it was possible to obtain the true size drawing of the vaults. The methodology, using the dense point cloud as initial data, consists in a succession of projections of the tracing drawings of orthophotos on a 3D model constituted by Nurbs surfaces that reproduce the geometry of the room. This procedure, however, consists in a series of extremely "time consuming" steps.

A new project started by the Faculty of Architecture and Mechanical Engineering of the University of Florence is reviewing this technique in order to reduce time and errors due to the long and cumbersome procedure, semi-automating and reducing the number of steps.

At the end of the project it will be able to obtain photographic images of vaults and their "unrolling" and the CAD drawing, where it will be possible to apply the degradation mapping and to plan the restoration.

ILLUSION AND ARCHITECTURE IN TUSCANY

Introduction

The study of the frescoes in illusionistic perspective of the Baroque and post-baroque period is fairly recent in Italy. After the first conference about Quadraturism that took place in Rimini in 2002, a national committee of experts was founded to promote and coordinate the studies about this topic. The above committee in made up of different researchers from different disciplines, history of art, architecture, mathematics, drawing and survey, because of the complexity of the prospective constructs that characterize the paintings.

The results from the latest researches and experimentation activities, performed on the ground-floor rooms of Pitti Palace, have been the starting point of a new research, which includes as partners the Department of Architecture and the Faculty of Engineering of University of Florence, target to devising new semi-automatic

systems for documenting digital measurement and representation of the painted surfaces.

Illusion of painted architecture

Quadraturism spread in Italy between the 17th and 18th century from the central regions, Emilia Romagna and Tuscany, to the whole national territory. It represents the highest expression of baroque applied to wall painting and consists in the representation of complex systems that include perspective architecture and figures in order to expand the dimensions of the halls in which they were represented, often in palaces and churches.

Figure 1. The painted vault and walls of gallery in Feroni palace, Florence

The virtual architecture painted on walls and ceilings is the basis of artistic deception. The painters copied colors and materials already present in the room, including real elements such as frames, columns and windows in the complex compositional structure to flout the perception of the observer. Even light and its direction had an important role in the definition of the painted space; as a matter of fact it was necessary to strictly respect the consistency between real and virtual parts.

The treatise about optics, scenery and perspective was widespread in those years and contained practical knowledge about techniques which were fundamental to artists, who paid high attention to such themes: “polyfocal perspective” (a technique that allowed the viewer to navigate through the painted rooms and still have a clear global vision of the artwork); “anamorphosis, (the deformation of a given image through its projection foreshortened by a chosen point on a flat or curved surface); the “accelerated perspective” (intended to make rooms wider thanks to some artifice in the perspective construction, such as raising the horizon line and representing the lateral walls in foreshortening).

The Bolognese painters Agostino Mitelli and Angelo Michele Colonna played an important role in the spread of painting of architecture and figures in Tuscany, their experience was followed as a model by the Florentine artists. They were en

Figure 2. Anamorphosis of an arch in Saint Ignatius's hallway painted by Andrea Pozzo

gaged in decorations for the apartment of Ferdinand II in Pitti Palace, now Museo degli Argenti, in the first half of the seventeenth century. Their Florentine disciple Jacopo Chiavistelli, more than twenty years later, continued the modernization of the ground floor of the Palazzo Pitti, in 1661 working on the apartment of Cosimo III in the right wing of the Palace and ten years after on the Vittoria della Rovere's complex. In both cases he demonstrated his skill in the execution of architectural composition and perspective and showed the acquisition of the full teachings of the masters about the practice of deception of the eye.

The two apartments are both composed by a succession of rectangular rooms "enfilade". The painted decorations start from the base of the walls and end at the center of the vault with the so-called "sfondato", in which are usually represented the figures of divinities to whom are the rooms dedicated. Today the rooms are occupied by the Superintendence offices and several furniture are against the walls, making it difficult to read the paintings.

THE SURVEY OF PAINTED VAULTS IN PITTI PALACE

3D survey

The accurate and dependable drawing of a building is the basic tool for architectural restoration, both for the knowledge of the state of conservation and both the definition of necessary interventions to improve the state of conservation. In order to achieve the previous goals, it is necessary to acquire the right amount of data in order to produce enough drawings that contain the geometric representation of the product, together with the conservation status of the object and its materials: in other words through plans, elevations and cross sections on which to affix the mapping of deterioration. This operation has the aim to define and quantify the interventions even from an economic standpoint.

The diagnosis of the state of conservation and the exact evaluation of the restoration works is possible only if the analysis is performed on drawings that reproduce in full size all the parts of the object under study, without any foreshortened portion. For architectural systems composed of planar elements only, although sophisticated and complex, this problem does not exist because it is possible to decompose them into flat elements and extract the two-dimensional drawings.

Figure 3. 3D model of the vault and of the fresco drawing

In order to represent a curved surface in true size, it is necessary to realize its “unrolling”, that is the representation on a plane of the pairs of curvilinear abscissa and the lines of impost.

The majority of traditional survey techniques are conceived to simplify as much as possible the measurement and representation of the object through discretization, however this means that they are limited in the description of complex curved surfaces.

The evolution of computer technology applied to survey gave birth to the digital three-dimensional survey with the introduction of the total station and the 3D laser scanner soon after. The use of the total station is closely related to a good discretization of the object that must be measured through the selection of the points that can describe its geometry. In the case of painted surfaces the topographical survey has to be matched with the photogrammetry and acquire a sufficient number of points as known as “supportive” points (easily recognizable in the photo) with relative coordinates. Unfortunately, the topographic survey combined with photogrammetry for the measurement of the curved and painted surfaces does not provide an accurate control of the error on the total surface.

With the introduction of the laser scanner, it was possible to decrease the possibility of error because the acquired points provide color data related to the reflectance of the materials, or in the case where the 3D scanner is equipped with a camera, to the real colors of the decorated surfaces, thus offering a description “continuous” and detailed of chromatic quality of the scanned object.

In addition, the dense point cloud allows to extrapolate three-dimensional models composed by triangular meshes or NURBS. On this kind of surfaces it is possible to project, with a CAD software, the traced vectors derived from orthographic views of the point cloud or from orthophotos previously made and calibrated on the cloud. Then it is possible to realize the un-rolling of the surface and of the paintings reported on the surface, getting the essential true size elaborate, for the representation of the results of diagnostic studies and the project of any restoration.

Figure 4. Digital unrolling of the fresco on the vault of Giustizia hall, Pitti Palace, Florence. The grid highlights the performance of the optical deformation.

CONCLUSIONS

The presently procedure for the unrolling of the surface and the painted decorations on it, in order to obtain the drawing in real size, consists of a series of phases which are extremely “time consuming”. Referring to the simplest case study of the barrel vault, it is first necessary to extrapolate a “best-fit” surface (semi-cylinder) directly from the point cloud. Subsequently it is possible to exploit the color data to extrapolate at least three views of the vault: it is in fact evident that the decorations in correspondence of zones in foreshortened compared to the view point are not very detailed (Figure 5).

The next step is to import the previous views in a CAD software in order to manually “trace” the relevant curves of decoration and get the corresponding vector data.

The vector “tracings” are finally projected onto the best-fitting surface and proceed to the unrolling of the surface and vector data themselves. The partial developments need a further process that consists in the correction of common areas by interpolation of the curves.

Obviously, the process described above is complicated in the case in which the vault is of groin type and, of course, is not applicable in the case where the vault is of dome type.

Figure 5. View from bottom (a) and from the side (b) of the vault

The objective of this research project proved to be effective in accelerating the process of true size representation of the frescoes by semi-automatic computer-based techniques. In particular, these tools will allow:

1. Automatic identification of unrolling surface types that may be present in the point cloud (segmentation),
2. "Ideal" surfaces reconstruction that best approximates the identified regions (as mentioned earlier this aspect is currently carried out manually),
3. The projection of the color data coming from the point cloud on "ideal" surfaces, in order to obtain a version which can also contain the vector decoration;
4. The unrolling of flat surfaces and the generation of the corresponding unrolled image;
5. The correction and the filling of any portion of the image due to the incomplete process of reconstruction;
6. Automatic vectorization through the use of methodologies based on "image processing" obtained in the previous step.

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